

Abstract

Geographic information systems (GIS) have been extensively used in various domains, including transportation science, criminology, urban planning, and epidemiology. Domain experts adopt spatial analysis tools in GIS, including kernel density visualization (KDV), inverse distance weighting (IDW), K-function, and Moran's I, to discover hidden patterns of location datasets. However, with the ever-growing location dataset sizes, all these tools are computationally expensive, which cannot efficiently (or even feasibly) support large-scale location datasets in the contemporary GIS (e.g., QGIS and ArcGIS). There are three main reasons. First, existing methods for supporting these tools normally take at least quadratic time complexities. Second, there is a lack of research studies for reducing the time complexities of these tools. Third, various fast algorithms have not been incorporated into GIS tools. To address these issues, we have proposed fast algorithms for handling some spatial analysis tools, including (1) KDV, (2) network KDV (NKDV), (3) spatiotemporal KDV (STKDV), (4) line density visualization (LDV), and (5) network K-function. These algorithms achieve the lower time complexities, enabling up to 1,000x speedups for million-scale datasets under a single CPU setting compared with existing methods. Moreover, we have already developed two QGIS plugins, called [Fast Density Analysis](#) and [Fast Line Density Analysis](#) (based on the algorithms for (1) to (3) and (4), respectively), which are online for use. For example, Fast Density Analysis can generate a 1280×960-resolution KDV in the New York traffic accident dataset (~1.5 million data points) with at most 40 seconds. In contrast, QGIS takes more than one day to generate this KDV. In the future, we plan to develop complexity-reduced algorithms and the corresponding plugins for other tools, including IDW, spatial/spatiotemporal K-function, and Moran's I. We anticipate that these plugins can replace the computationally expensive implementations in QGIS/ArcGIS so that domain experts can efficiently analyze large-scale location datasets.